

Interaction of Iodine Monochloride with Substances Containing the Reactive Methylene Group.

BY K. G. NAIK AND C. C. SHAH.

Although the chloro- and bromo-derivatives of substituted malonamides have been extensively prepared and studied (Baakes, West and Whiteley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 362; West, *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 2196; 1924, 125, 710; 1925, 127, 748; Naik and Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 11), iodo-derivatives of the same are not known. However, di-iodomalonic acid and methyl di-iodomalonate have been prepared by Willstätter (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1377), who describes them as very unstable substances decomposing spontaneously at ordinary temperature.

Moreover, in view of the fact that the chloromalonamides are more stable than the bromomalonamides (West, *loc. cit.*), it was expected that iodomalonamides will be very reactive and will thus form an interesting subject for the study of the effect of the adjoining groups on the two hydrogen atoms of the reactive methylene group, which problem is being tackled in this laboratory for the last several years (Naik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 379 and subsequent papers).

With this end in view, the interaction of iodine monochloride with the following substances was studied:—

(1) Malondipropylamide, (2) malondiheptylamide, (3) malonamide, (4) malondibenzylamide, (5) malondiphenylamide, (6) malondi-*o*-tolylamide, (7) malondi-*p*-tolylamide, (8) malon-dimethylphenylamide, (9) malondi-*a*-naphthylamide, (10) malon-monophenylamide, (11) malonmono-*p*-tolylamide, (12) methylmalon-diphenylamide, and (13) methylmalondi-*o*-tolylamide.

The use of iodine monochloride as an iodinating agent is well known (Schützenberger, *Z. Chem. Pharm.*, 1861, 5, 1; Michael and Norton, *Ber.*, 1878, 11, 108; Ostermeyer, C, 1884, 937; Wheeler and Liddle, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1909, 42, 441; C., 1910, I, 528; Willgerodt and Arnold, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3344; Cofman, *Gassetta*, 1920, II, 50, 296; C., 1921, I, 943) specially in the case of aromatic compounds. It was expected that here also, iodo-derivatives of the substituted malonamides will be obtained. But contrary to our expectations we only obtained chloro-derivatives many of which have already been prepared by Naik and Shah (*loc. cit.*).

Of the compounds investigated, in the case of (1), (2), (3), (4), (6), (7) and (11), the reactive methylene group was converted into $\cdot\text{CCl}_2$ without the halogenation of the nucleus, while in the case of (9), the nucleus was also attacked and $\text{CCl}_2(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHC}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{Cl})_2$ was obtained. In the case of (8) and (10), only one hydrogen atom of the methylene group was attacked with the formation of the —CHCl group, the nuclei in the case of (8) remaining unaffected. In the case of (12) and (13), having only one available hydrogen in the methylene group, $\text{MeCCl}(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHC}_8\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$ and $\text{MeCCl}(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHC}_7\text{H}_5\text{Cl})_2$ were formed.

Malon-diphenylamide (5) forms a curious exception, for in this case the methylene group remains intact, the nuclei only being halogenated, giving rise to $\text{CH}_2(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$. The same compound was obtained by Naik and Trivedi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 239) by the action of selenium tetrachloride on the same substance.

The method for differentiating the chlorine atoms in the methylene group from those in the nucleus was the same as the one adopted by Naik and Shah (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The amide (1 mol.) was treated with iodine monochloride (4 mols.) in presence of chloroform. After allowing the reaction mixture to remain at ordinary temperature (30°) for twentyfour hours, it was refluxed on a water-bath for three hours. The chloroform solution was then shaken with 10 per cent. sodium thiosulphate to remove free iodine and after separation from the aqueous layer was evaporated to dryness. The resulting solid was crystallised from a suitable solvent. In the case of dichloromalonylamide, nothing was recovered from the chloroform solution, so the white mass adhering to the flask was extracted with water, and was boiled till all the iodine volatilised; the solution was then concentrated when the product separated.

In this way, malon-dipropylamide gave rise to dichloromalonydipropylamide (Naik and Shah), malondiheptylamide to dichloromalondiheptylamide (Naik and Trivedi), malonylamide to dichloromalonylamide (Backes, West and Whiteley), malondibenzylamide to dichloromalondibenzylamide (N. and S.), malondiphenylamide to malondichlorophenylamide (N. and T.), malondi-*o*-tolylamide to dichlo-

romalondi-*o*-tolylamide (N. and S.), malondi-*p*-tolylamide to dichloromalondi-*p*-tolylamide (N. and S.), malondimethylphenylamide to monochloromalondimethylphenylamide (N. and S.), and malonmono-*p*-tolylamide to dichloromalonmono-*p*-tolylamide (N. and S.).

Dichloromalondichloro-o-naphthylamide was obtained from one g. of the amide and 4 g. of iodine monochloride. It was recrystallised from benzene as white needles, m.p. 191°. It is fairly soluble in alcohol, benzene and chloroform but slightly so in petroleum. (Found: Cl, 28·71; Cl(malonyl), 14·44. $C_{23}H_{14}O_2N_2Cl_4$ requires Cl, 28·92; Cl (malonyl), 14·46 per cent.)

Monochloromalonmonochlorophenylamide.—One g. of the amide and 6 g. of iodine monochloride in 25 c.c. of chloroform were taken. The white substance was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 152°.

It is easily soluble in alcohol, benzene, chloroform and acetic acid; but almost insoluble in light petroleum. (Found: Cl, 28·35; Cl (malonyl), 14·80. $C_9H_8O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 28·86; Cl (malonyl), 14·43 per cent.)

Methylchloromalondichlorophenylamide.—One g. of methylmalondiphenylamide and 4 g. of iodine monochloride were used. The product separated from benzene; m.p. 164°. It is very soluble in chloroform, acetone and ether but less so in benzene and alcohol. (Found: Cl, 28·31; Cl (malonyl), 9·74. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N_2Cl_3$ requires Cl, 28·67; Cl (malonyl), 9·55 per cent.)

Methylchloromalondichloro-o-tolylamide was obtained by the interaction of 3·5 g. iodine monochloride with 1 g. methylmalondi-*o*-tolylamide in 25 c.c. chloroform. It crystallises in fine needles from benzene and melts at 184°. It is very soluble in acetone but less so in benzene, alcohol and chloroform, and insoluble in petroleum. (Found: Cl, 26·74; Cl (malonyl), 9·31. $C_{18}H_{17}O_2N_2Cl_3$ requires Cl, 26·62; Cl (malonyl), 8·88 per cent.)

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